

CONSTITUTIONAL CONSOLIDATION OF INTERNATIONAL HARMONY

Sayfitdinova Madinabonu Shaxitbek qizi

ADPI Department of Social and Humanities teacher

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Abstract: In this article, the constitutional strengthening of inter-ethnic harmony is widely and comprehensively covered on the basis of scientific evidence.

In any independent country, the people's free living, happy marriage, realization of their will, noble intentions should be legally guaranteed. This guarantee creates conditions for ensuring the development of the Motherland, the independence of the state, the cohesion of the people, international friendship and solidarity, and the stability of independence. The day of adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which created such guaranteed conditions, became an incomparable historical date in the life of the Uzbek people. In it, representatives of nations of different nationalities, languages, and social origins, i.e., Uzbek people's prospects for the future, future destiny were determined.

In fact, our country is one of the mono-ethnic (multi-ethnic) countries. Today, representatives of more than 135 nationalities and peoples live in our republic. The process of integration of nationalities, nations and peoples has been taking place in our country for centuries, and their social, cultural, spiritual and religious values have been absorbed and refined over time.

As noted in the preface of our General Council, "The people of Uzbekistan: solemnly declaring their loyalty to human rights and the ideas of state sovereignty, realizing their high responsibility to the present and future generations, relying on the historical experience of the development of Uzbek statehood, democracy and showing commitment to social justice, recognizing the supremacy of universally recognized rules of international law, striving to ensure that the citizens of the republic live a decent life, aiming to establish a humane democratic legal state, in order to ensure civil peace and national harmony, "accepts this Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the form of its autonomous representatives". Democratic principles are also reflected in the fact that these articles in the preamble of our constitution are written on behalf of the people of Uzbekistan. As stated in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "The people of Uzbekistan are made up of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan, regardless of their nationality."¹

This idea is the moral basis for establishing and strengthening mutual respect, friendship and solidarity between people of different nationalities and ethnicities living in one society and working towards a common goal. As a legal guarantee of this, in our General Dictionary, "All citizens in the Republic of Uzbekistan have the same rights and freedoms, regardless of gender, race, nationality, language, religion, social origin, belief, personal and social status. , are equal before the law. We can also see the example of Article 18, which stipulates that privileges are determined only by law and must be in accordance with the principles of social justice.

The National Idea, formed during the years of independence, creates conditions for the full realization of the talent and potential of the representative of each nation and mobilizes it towards such noble goals as the development of the Motherland, the peace of the country and

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Конституцияси. – Т.: Ўзбекистон 2023. – 6-бет.

the well-being of the people, and they move towards one goal. unites From the essence of the first chapter of our Constitution, called Basic Principles, it is constitutionally guaranteed to respect the languages of all nationalities and peoples living in the territory of our country, their customs and traditions that have been formed historically, and ensures the creation of necessary conditions for their development. We can see the implementation of this norm in the example of National Centers operating in our country today. This is of great importance in the development of culture, art, spirituality and social relations of representatives of different nationalities and passing them on to future generations.

One of the most important factors of social development is the unity between the nation that gave the name (title) to a certain country and other peoples living in it. On the contrary, failure to understand the importance of the national idea can derail society's life, peace and stability. The Constitution plays an important role in preventing such unpleasant situations. "Citizens are obliged to comply with the Constitution and laws, to respect the rights, freedoms, honor and dignity of other people." provides and defines. In addition, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates that the state expresses the will of the people, serves its interests, and that state bodies and officials are responsible to society and citizens.

Aggressive nationalism and chauvinism are the evil that destroys international harmony and harmony. It is inevitable that a society under the influence of such harmful ideas will turn into a state of instability. A clear example of this is fascism, which troubled the nations of Europe in the 20th century and caused the decline of some countries, or the idea of communism, which was based on the idea of false internationalism and did not take into account national characteristics.

Today, in the era of global processes, the life rules guaranteed by our Constitution are of great importance in ensuring the cohesion of our people, maintaining inter-ethnic harmony and the development of their cultures. After all, representatives of many nationalities and peoples have been living together on the land of Uzbekistan since ancient times. The fact that there have been no national disputes between them for centuries shows the eternal tolerance of our people.